

Colorimetric Determination of Fenitrothion and Methyl Parathion using a Hydroxylaminolytic Procedure

N. RAMAKRISHNA and B. V. RAMACHANDRAN*

Indian Drug Research Laboratory, Poona 411005

Manuscript received 11 January 1977, revised 12 September 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

The liberation of *p*-nitro-*m*-cresol (PNC) and *p*-nitrophenol (PNP) from fenitrothion (*o*, *o*-dimethyl *o*-*p*-nitro-*m*-cresyl phosphorothionate) and methyl parathion (*o*, *o*-dimethyl *o*-*p*-nitrophenyl phosphorothionate) respectively by alkali alone is a slow process, but the rate can be increased many hundred fold by substituting alkali with a mixture of 0.5*N* sodium hydroxide and 0.67 *M* hydroxylamine. The reaction is almost instantaneous at room temperature when the system also contains 33 per cent. ethanol. Taking advantage of the above finding a procedure has been worked out for the spectrophotometric determination of fenitrothion and methyl parathion via the PNC and PNP liberated. The method is simple and quantitative and avoids the drastic chemical steps involved in the currently available methods. The sensitivity is about 0.1 μ mole and the method can be used for the determination of the two insecticides in technical preparations, formulations and enzymic digests.

FENITROTHION (Sumithion, *O,O*-dimethyl *O-p*-nitro-*m*-cresyl phosphorothionate) and methyl parathion (*O,O*-dimethyl *O-p*-nitrophenyl phosphorothionate) are extensively used organophosphorus insecticides. The former differs from the latter in containing a methyl group in the meta position of the *p*-nitrophenyl moiety. Yet the presence of this "magic methyl group" somehow confers on the insecticide a high degree of selectivity¹. Whereas methyl parathion is equally toxic to both insects and mammals, fenitrothion is toxic to insects to the same extent as methyl parathion but is almost innocuous to mammals². Because of this reason fenitrothion is in much demand for use on food crops. Several reasons have been postulated for this selectivity³⁻⁵ based on the higher rate of detoxification of the compound in the mammalian system but the enzymes responsible have not been characterised.

We are interested in the metabolism of fenitrothion, and as a preliminary have developed a method for the extraction and determination of the residual fenitrothion and methyl parathion in enzymic digests. Whereas in the currently available procedures^{6,7} the *p*-nitrocresol (PNC) and *p*-nitrophenol (PNP) moieties have to be liberated by refluxing with alcoholic potassium hydroxide, a mixture of hydroxylamine and alkali easily hydrolyses the compounds at room temperature in a very short period. Though the method is primarily developed for application in biochemical studies, it can be used in the assay of the two insecticides in technical preparations and formulations.

Materials and Methods

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 colorimeter was used with tubes of 1 cm light path. The

samples of fenitrothion (95.4%) and methyl parathion (about 80%) were obtained through the courtesy of Bayer (India) Ltd., Bombay. Stock solutions containing 100 μ moles/ml (0.693 g of fenitrothion and 0.658 g of methyl parathion in 25 ml of ethanol) were prepared and preserved in the refrigerator. Other reagents were prepared as described previously^{8,9}. The isobutanol-benzene mixture¹⁰ used will be referred to as BB in the text. The calibration curves of PNP and PNC (obtained from the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona) drawn as described earlier⁹ were found to be identical.

Determination of free PNC and PNP: One ml of fenitrothion stock solution (or the sample) is blown into about 90 ml of 0.1 *N* hydrochloric acid which also contains 1 ml of 10% (w/v) Triton X-100. The volume is adjusted to 100 ml with acid and the mixture is vigorously shaken to obtain a uniform suspension. The solution contains 1 μ mole/ml of fenitrothion. In a separating funnel 10 ml of the suspension is shaken with 10 ml of BB for 1 min. The lower aqueous layer is discarded. The solvent layer is then gently shaken with 10 ml of 0.05 *N* sodium hydroxide which leaches out only the free PNC. The lower aqueous layer is filtered through a fluted filter paper and the absorbance determined at 410 nm. This value gives the free PNC in 10 μ mole of fenitrothion. The value for free PNP in methyl parathion can be determined in a similar manner.

Determination of fenitrothion and methyl parathion: The BB layer from above is dried by shaking with about a gram of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Of this aliquots of 0.4 ml in triplicate are pipetted into test-tubes of approx 15 \times 1.8 cm. The solvent is evaporated in an air-oven at 115 \pm 5°

(30-45 min). The tubes are then cooled to room temperature and 1 ml of ethanol added to each followed by 2 ml of freshly prepared (1+1) mixture of 3.5 *N* sodium hydroxide and 2 *M* hydroxylamine hydrochloride. After waiting for not less than 3 min the solution is diluted to 10 ml, filtered and the colour determined at 410 nm. The value can be read off from the standard graph wherein ethanol has been included. This value multiplied by 2.5 gives the fenitrothion content in 1 ml of the aqueous suspension. Methyl parathion is also determined as above. Technical preparations and formulations are treated as described for parathion⁹. In biochemical work, 10 ml of an enzymic digest is extracted with an equal volume of BB for the determination of free PNC or PNP and the un-reacted insecticide.

Results and Discussion

The results of the preliminary experiments which led to the development of the present method are given in Table 1. The experimental details are as

TABLE 1—RATE OF HYDROLYSIS OF FENITROTHION, FENITRO-OXON AND METHYL PARATHION TO PNC AND PNP IN VARIOUS MEDIA

Expt No.	Medium	Half-life in minutes		
		Fenitro-thion	Fenitro-oxon	Methyl parathion
1.	0.5 <i>N</i> NaOH aqueous	778	1.5	452
2.	0.5 <i>N</i> NaOH - 33% ethanolic	198	1.7	41
3.	0.5 <i>N</i> NaOH + 0.67 <i>M</i> hydroxylamine - aqueous	23	Too rapid	1.2
4.	As above - 33% ethanolic	0.5 to 1.1	Too rapid	Too rapid
5.	0.5 <i>N</i> NaOH, 33% ethanolic + 0.05 <i>M</i> hydroxylamine	18		
6.	As above with 0.1 <i>M</i> hydroxylamine	4.3		
7.	" " 0.2 <i>M</i> " "	2.0		
8.	" " 0.3 <i>M</i> " "	1.1		
9.	" " 0.4 <i>M</i> " "	0.9 to 1.1		

given for EPN (O-ethyl O-*p*-nitrophenyl phenylphosphonothioate)⁸ and parathion⁹. It is seen that the half-life of fenitrothion in 0.5 *N* alkali which is 778 min at 20° is reduced nearly a thousand-fold in the presence of 0.67 *M* hydroxylamine and 33% ethanol. The reaction is almost instantaneous at room temperature (25-30°). There is a similar reduction in the half-life of methyl parathion. It is also seen that in the case of fenitro-oxon, the oxygen analogue of fenitrothion, the half-life is uniformly low with or without hydroxylamine. The fenitro-oxon was prepared by oxidation of fenitrothion by bromine water and the extent of conversion monitored as for parathion¹¹. Experiments were also done with methyl paraoxon but the reaction rate was too rapid and the results are therefore not included in the table. Since the oxygen analogues are more rapidly hydrolysed than the thio compounds there is a possibility that the catalysis due to hydro-

xylamine may involve an intermediate step of conversion of the thio to the oxo form. To determine this, the degradation product of fenitrothion, viz., O, O-dimethyl phosphoric ester was isolated by extraction with a solvent from an acidic solution according to the principles given by Ramachandran¹². The isolated substance was found to have the same R₁ value as O, O-dimethyl phosphorothioate when chromatographed according to Plapp and Casida¹³ and to be different from O, O-dimethyl phosphate which was the product isolated by hydrolysis of fenitro-oxon. The same thio compound was isolated during the degradation of methyl parathion. These results show that during the hydrolysis of fenitrothion and methyl parathion by hydroxylamine and sodium hydroxide the products formed are O, O-dimethyl phosphorothioate and PNC or PNP. This was further confirmed by qualitative tests on the phosphoric acid ester after sodium fusion when the presence of sulphur was confirmed.

The exact role of hydroxylamine in speeding the hydrolytic rate of fenitrothion, methyl parathion and other PNP-containing insecticides^{5,6} is not clear, but expts 5-9 in Table 1 indicate that the reaction rate is dependent to some extent on the concentration of hydroxylamine. This is in agreement with the findings of Jandorf¹⁴ who showed that hydroxylamine reacts with organophosphates like DFP (diisopropyl phosphorofluoridate) and sarin (O-isopropyl methyl phosphonofluoridate) in accordance with the following equation:

From this it is clear that the role of hydroxylamine is not merely catalytic but that it is actually taking part in the reaction.

It is now well documented that nucleophiles such as hydroxylamine, oxamate ions, hydrogen peroxide ions and O-Cl groups, which show common structural features of an electronegative atom with un-shared electrons alpha to the attacking atom, all exhibit reactivity towards phosphoryl phosphorus much greater than would be predicted from their basicities. This phenomenon has been referred to as "α-effect" by Edwards and Pearson¹⁵, but the mechanism has not been fully understood. It is obvious that in the hydroxylaminolytic procedure developed in this paper the above effect is responsible for the accelerated rate of reaction. The spectacularly enhanced effect on the thio compounds as compared to the oxygen analogues is still not clear. In addition to the effect of hydroxylamine, the presence of ethanol seems to accelerate the reaction still further. The reason may be that alkoxide ions are more effective than hydroxide ions^{16,17}.

Certain quaternary oximes such as 2-pyridine aldoxime methiodide or methochloride (2-PAM) are effective antidotes against poisoning by organophosphorus insecticides¹⁸. Their antidotal effect

is due to their ability to make a nucleophilic attack on the phosphoric ester moiety after the organophosphate has formed a covalent bond via the serine hydroxyl group with the vital enzyme acetylcholinesterase. The phosphoric ester is thus detached and the enzyme reactivated. It may be mentioned that one of the early reactivators tried was hydroxylamine^{19,20} which was, however, found to be considerably less effective than the quaternary oximes. We attempted a comparative study of the effectiveness of 2-PAM (which is an extensively used antidote against organophosphorus insecticide poisoning) and hydroxylamine on the rate of hydrolysis of parathion *in vitro*. The results are given in Table 2. It is seen that 2-PAM is very much less

TABLE 2—RATE OF LIBERATION OF *p*-NITROPHENOL FROM PARATHION WITH HYDROXYLAMINE AND 2-PYRIDINE ALDOXIME METHOCHLORIDE* AS CATALYSIS

(The media contained 0.5N NaOH and 93% ethanol in all cases. Half-lives were calculated from first order rate constants at 20°. Experimental details are as given in refs. 8 and 9)

Molar concn. of catalyst	Half-life in minutes in presence of	
	Hydroxylamine	2-PAM
0.025	178	647
0.05	74	627
0.1	28	579
0.2	22	523
0.4	10	502
0.5	6	463
0.67	3.7	325

* A product of Aldrich Chemical Co., Inc., Milwaukee, Wis., USA.

effective than equimolar concentrations of hydroxylamine in the hydrolysis of parathion. Whereas, as a reactivator of phosphorylated acetylcholinesterase, 2-PAM is more effective than hydroxylamine, the reverse seems to be case with the hydrolysis of parathion itself. Obviously, in the case of the inhibited enzyme the quaternary ammonium group of 2-PAM helps by orienting the molecule before the oxime makes a nucleophilic attack on the P atom¹⁸ while this is not possible in the case of the organophosphate itself.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Dr. G. S. Pendse, Hony Director, for his interest and encouragement, and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for a research grant.

References

1. R. D. O'BRIEN, "Insecticides, Action and Metabolism," Academic Press, New York, 1967.
2. Y. NISHIZAWA, K. FUJII, T. KADOTA, J. MIYAMOTO and H. SAKAMOTO, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1961, **25**, 605.
3. A. VARDANIS and L. G. CRAWFORD, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1964, **57**, 336.
4. J. MIYAMOTO, *Residue Rev.*, 1969, **25**, 251.
5. R. M. HOLLINGWORTH, R. L. METCALF and T. R. FUKUTO, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1967, **15**, 242.
6. J. A. A. KETELAAR and J. E. HELLINGMAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 646.
7. "Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists", 11th Edition (Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC), 1970, p. 115.
8. V. M. BHAGWAT and B. V. RAMACHANDRAN, *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.*, 1974, **57**, 1283.
9. N. RAMAKRISHNA and B. V. RAMACHANDRAN, *Analyst* (London), 1976, **101**, 528.
10. J. M. MARTIN and D. M. DOTY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 965.
11. N. RAMAKRISHNA and B. V. RAMACHANDRAN, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1976, **13**, 190.
12. B. V. RAMACHANDRAN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1967, **21**, 609.
13. F. W. PLAPP and J. E. CASIDA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **30**, 1622.
14. B. J. JANDORF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3866.
15. J. O. EDWARDS and R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 19.
16. V. M. BHAGWAT, B. V. RAMACHANDRAN, and P. M. NAIR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 502.
17. J. R. COX and O. B. RAMSAY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 317.
18. F. HOBBIKER in *Handbuch der Experimentellen Pharmakologie*, Bd. XV, Ed. G. B. KORLLER, Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1963, p. 921.
19. I. B. WILSON, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **190**, 111.
20. I. B. WILSON, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1952, **199**, 113.